

A New Measuring Technique of the Corona Discharge Current Based on Electrostatic Induction

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Abstract—There are many methods currently used in industry and laboratories for measuring the electrical current, which are based on different physical phenomena. Each method offers advantages and drawbacks for current measurement, but the majority of them are based on contact measuring of either the drop voltage in a resistor or the flowing current. The aim of this paper is to develop a new technique based on the electrostatic induction for measurement of the corona discharge current generated by an electrostatic precipitator (ESP). The new patent pending method, which is a non contact measuring technique of the electrical current flowing in a conducting wire, is based on the measured voltage of a Faraday pail, induced by electrostatic induction. In the present work, this device is used for the evaluation of the corona discharge current generated by an electrostatic precipitator. Trichel pulses in the negative polarity were plotted for both cases with and without particles filtration. Obtained results have shown that this new non-contact technique gives as precise measurement values as the classic methods based on direct evaluation of current using an ammeter.

Index Terms—Electrostatic influence, Faraday pail, Electrostatic precipitator, discharge current measurement, Filtration efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

CURRENT sensing is used to perform two essential circuit functions. First, it is used to measure how much current is flowing in a circuit, which may be used to make decisions about turning off peripheral loads to conserve power or to return operation to normal limits. A second function is to determine when it is a too much or a fault condition. If current exceeds safe limits, a software or hardware interlock condition is met and provides a signal to turn off the application, perhaps a motor in a stalled condition or short circuit. It is essential to choose the appropriate technology with the necessary robustness to properly withstand the extreme conditions that can exist during a fault [1].

There are several ways for measuring the current flowing in a conducting wire. The power current transformer is a device which is widely used in industrial electrical engineering [2]. Due to its slow response, determined by the core magnetism, it cannot be used at a frequency higher than assigned (60 or 400Hz). At higher or lower frequency, its transmission ratio is distorted due to the nonlinear characteristics of the core magnification.

The Rogowski Coil is an alternating-current component sensor, measuring the current without contact. Due to the fast response and the high linearity, the sensor registers alternating and pulse current with high accuracy. However, the integration scheme generates distortion on direct current linked with the accumulative error during registration of the high frequency transient phenomenon and insensitivity to the low frequency current changes [3].

Hall Effect sensor is a transducer of which its output voltage (V_{out}) varies in reaction to a magnetic field. This

type of sensor is used for proximity switching, speed detection, positioning and current sensing applications. In its simplest form, it operates like an analog transducer, thus directly returning a voltage. Its distance from the Hall plate can be determined with a known magnetic field. The electricity which is carried through a conductor will produce a magnetic field which varies according to the current [4]. The sensor can therefore be used in order to measure the current without interrupting the circuit. The sensor is typically integrated with a permanent magnet or a wound core that surrounds the conductor to be measured.

The aim of the present work is the development of a new method of current measuring, patent pending, for measuring a discharge current generated by an electric discharge such as the corona or the dielectric barrier discharge. This device comprises an electrostatic sensor which measures the current without contact with the conducting wire. Nowadays, the devices used to measure the current are all based on the magnetic field produced by the current itself. In this paper, a new method based on the measure of the electric charge or the potential induced on a Faraday pail, is described. Experiments were performed for measuring the corona discharge current produced by an electrostatic precipitator (ESP).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The experimental setup used in this work (Fig.1), comprises three distinct functional units: the admission of powder, the ESP and the measuring set.

The filtration device is a conventional wire-to-cylinder ESP type placed on a horizontal plane, of 900mm length and 100mm diameter. A stainless steel wire of diameter 200 μ m is connected to a negative high voltage supply ($U_{max} = 40kV$, $I_{max} = 7.5mA$, Spellman SL 40).

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Fig. 1. Descriptive (schematic) of the electrostatic effect sensor for measuring the potential induced by the corona discharge current.

The admission of PVC micronized particles of average diameter $40\mu\text{m}$, used as pollutant product, is provided by means of a vibratory feeder which introduces it into the ESP, through a funnel placed at the inlet of the filter. A same sample of mass $m = 80\text{g}$ was used for each experiment, with a constant mass flow equal to $60\text{g}/\text{min}$. The speed of the product flow in the ESP is controlled by means of a cyclone filter ($Q_{max} = 150\text{m}^3/\text{h}$) which is by the way used to recover the unfiltered powder in order to estimate the filtration outcome of the ESP.

The method proposed for assessing the ESP performance is based on the measurement of the corona discharge current, flowing in the wire connected to ground, a portion of which is placed inside a Faraday pail. A series resistance, used to prevent the rapid dissipation of the current towards ground, is placed downstream the Faraday pail, as shown in Fig.1. A picoscope 3207B is used for direct measurement of the voltage induced in the Faraday pail by the DC negative discharge voltage. The measurements are displayed on a PC (Fig.3).

Figure 2 shows the schematic of the current sensor used to measure and visualize the corona discharge. The proposed technique consists in measuring the current without contact, by electrostatic induction.

Fig. 2. Descriptive (schematic) of the electrostatic effect sensor for measuring the potential induced by the corona discharge current.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measurement results of the discharge current in the ESP by using the conventional method, using a micro ammeter, were compared with those obtained with the new system. A resistance of $500\ \Omega$ was placed in series with the circuit (Fig.4). The plotted values of the current were obtained by dividing the voltage measured using the picoscope by the series resistance. The average discharge current is estimated by measuring the induced voltage (V_{ind}) applied on the cylinders of the Faraday pail, by using the picoscope connected at the electrostatic sensor. The current is calculated using equation (1):

$$I_d = \frac{V_{ind}}{R} \quad (1)$$

where R is the series resistance.

Obtained results shown in Fig.4 point out that there is a remarkable analogy between the two methods, which confirms the measurement precision of the electrostatic sensor device. The non contact device allows obtaining precise values in comparison with the ammeter. Furthermore, at the opposite of the micro-ammeter which cannot measure the current of about nA , the electrostatic sensor in combination with the picoscope, allows to measure such values of the current. As seen in Fig.5, the new device measures small current down to 0.5nA .

3.1 Visualization of the corona discharge current

Using the electrostatic sensor, the corona discharge current could be visualized as shown in Fig.6 and Fig.8. The non contact sensor allows visualizing the impulsions of the current with precision.

A detailed visualization of one Trichel pulse may also be obtained by using the electrostatic sensor. As seen in Fig.7, a pulse amplitude of 0.6mA is obtained with a pulse duration of about $0.8\mu\text{s}$. With further increase in voltage (Fig.8), the pulses become more dense and more regular. The plotted diagram in Fig.9, obtained for $U = -19\text{kV}$, the pulse duration is about $0.9\mu\text{s}$ with an amplitude of the discharge current reaching 3.75mA .

The new measuring device was used to estimate the corona discharge current produced by the ESP, with and without filtration, for the same applied voltage $U = -16\text{kV}$. Obtained diagrams of the Trichel pulses represented in Fig.10 point out a clear difference between both cases, with and without filtration of micronized PVC particles.

Fig. 3. Photography of the experimental setup.

Fig. 4. Comparison between Current-voltage characteristics of the negative corona discharge in the ESP ($d = 50\text{mm}$) measured by the microammeter and the electrostatic effect sensor ($R = 500\Omega$).

Fig. 5. Current of discharge as functions of low Voltage values applied in the ESP ($d = 50\text{mm}$) measured by the electrostatic effect sensor ($R = 1\text{M}\Omega$).

Fig. 7. Waveform details of one isolated pulse obtained for $U = -9\text{kV}$.

Fig. 8. Waveforms of the Trichel pulses for $U = -19\text{kV}$ in the ESP ($d = 50\text{mm}$), $R = 500\Omega$.

Fig. 6. Waveforms of the Trichel pulses for $U = -9 \text{ kV}$ in the ESP ($d = 50\text{mm}$), $R = 500\Omega$.

Fig. 9. Waveform details of one isolated pulse obtained for $U = -19\text{kV}$.

Fig. 10. Waveforms of the Trichel pulses for $U = -16\text{kV}$ in the ESP ($d = 50\text{mm}$; $R = 500\Omega$), with and without particles.

4 CONCLUSION

An experimental study was conducted in the present work to validate a new measurement technique of the corona discharge current generated in the ESP, based on electrostatic induction. Obtained results have shown that this new technique gives precise measurement values as the classic methods based on direct evaluation of the current using an

ammeter. The principal advantages of this patent pending device is the evaluation of any current without contact and the possibility to measure as small current as nA with a high precision. Further analysis is required to apply it for measuring different types of current depending on their amplitude and frequency.

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